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COMMUNICATION WITH NEUROLOGICAL PATIENTS: A PUBLIC POLICY PERSPECTIVE

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***Abstract:** Medical communication is an important element in the doctor-patient relationship. Special attention must be paid to neurological patients and how they are communicated with. They often feel vulnerable due to health problems and unfamiliar people, frequently having poor memory and confused thinking. Particularly, emphasis must be placed on obtaining informed consent and respecting their confidentiality. Effective medical communication will help the doctor achieve their goals in dialogue with the patient and improve the outcomes of their professional activity.*

***Keywords:** Public policy, medical communication, neurological patients, informed consent, confidentiality.*

Introduction

Medical communication is an essential element in medical practice and in the doctor-patient relationship. This process is complex and involves multiple actors, such as doctors, patients, and healthcare institutions. By recognizing the importance of communication, medical workers can achieve their goals of promoting valuable ideas beneficial to society. Effective treatment, resulting from coordinated dialogue, will support a good relationship between doctor and patient. All forms of communication, whether verbal, nonverbal, paraverbal, or extraverbal, are useful and truly beneficial, contributing to the accurate diagnosis of

the patient and the selection of an appropriate treatment. Similarly, ongoing communication among medical workers from different medical specialties should not be overlooked, as active collaboration and effective communication also serve the patient's interests. In this context, public institutions play a significant role, as they are responsible for managing ethical and communication issues that may arise in the relationships between doctors and patients, or between medical institutions and society. Collaboration between medical staff and public institutions would be advantageous for the development and promotion of effective health policies, which would prevent, monitor, and resolve ethical dilemmas, and protect the rights of patients as well as those of medical workers.

Building on what has been said, in this article we aim to study the specifics of medical communication in neurology, with a focus on obtaining informed consent and protecting the confidentiality of neurological patients.

1. Medical communication: informed consent and confidentiality as core elements

In the specialized literature, we note several interpretations of the concept of *medical communication*:

- ✓ E. Phillips Polack and Theodore A. Avtgis define it as a „pragmatic method used by healthcare providers and their patients in daily interactions” (Polack, 2010, p.125).
- ✓ Robert C. Smith argues that „medical communication refers to the exchange of information related to health and medicine between health professionals, patients, and other interested parties, including a wide range of activities such as the dissemination of scientific research, patient education, and care coordination among medical teams” (Smith, 2012).
- ✓ Oana Atomei concludes that medical communication plays an important role in developing a trusting relationship, and the patient's trust in the doctor is one of the most important aspects when it correlates with the outcome of care” (Atomei, 2018, p.177).

Referring to *neurological medical communication*, we emphasize that it includes interactions between neurologists, patients, and their families. It aids in the accurate diagnosis of the patient, the development of a personalized medical treatment plan, continuous monitoring of disease progression, and medication adjustment.

In dialogue with neurological patients, it is essential for the doctor to be not only an excellent speaker but also an attentive listener. They should demonstrate a range of professional skills, which include obtaining the patient's informed consent and maintaining the patient's confidentiality.

1.1. The concept of informed consent

Informed consent represents the patient's agreement with the treatment proposed by the doctor. It involves informing the patient about all aspects of the treatment, including the benefits and potential risks involved. It can only be obtained in the context of a constructive, coherent, and empathetic dialogue, with the doctor ensuring that the patient maintains their autonomy and the right to make the final decision regarding their treatment.

During the dialogue, the principles of bioethics are respected. According to the principle of autonomy, the patient must be thoroughly informed about their health issues, know all possible treatments, be aware of their benefits and risks, and independently decide the best option for themselves. Following the principles of non-maleficence and beneficence, the patient should not be harmed and must be satisfied with the outcomes achieved. Consistent with the principle of justice, all rights of the patient and the doctor must be respected.

In the process of doctor-patient communication, it is essential for the doctor to demonstrate honesty and empathy. Being honest is not difficult when the doctor deeply understands the challenges the patient is facing and collaborates with them to overcome these challenges together. An honest doctor will earn the patient's full trust, which will contribute to better treatment adherence and increased patient satisfaction. Therefore, obtaining informed consent is essential in medical practice and can only

be achieved through a transparent, honest dialogue in accordance with ethical and professional standards.

1.2. The confidentiality in healthcare

The concept of confidentiality involves the responsibility to protect patients' personal and medical information so that it is not accessed, disclosed, or used improperly. In neurology, respecting confidentiality is fundamental to maintaining a trust relationship between patients and doctors. Patients are often required to share sensitive personal information with their doctors, trusting that it will not be used against them. Being assured of the doctor's confidentiality, the patient will be honest and not omit details. Maintaining confidentiality is essential not only for legal compliance but also for fostering a respectful approach towards the individual dignity of each patient.

The disclosure of information regarding a patient's health condition, private life, or family life can only occur in exceptional cases, such as the risk of spreading communicable diseases, at the justified request of law enforcement agencies or judicial authorities. Information that constitutes professional secrecy may only be shared with other parties with the explicit consent of the patients or their legal representatives, or if the disclosure does not harm their condition.

2. Obtaining Informed Consent and Protecting Patient Confidentiality

2.1. Regarding informed consent

The challenges that can arise in obtaining informed consent require rigorous ethical approaches, often involving personalized solutions for each individual case. It is essential for doctors to collaborate with medical ethics teams and to engage in ongoing dialogue with patients and their families to obtain informed consent.

To support and guide the physicians in their practice, various regulations have been adopted and implemented that aim to protect

patients' rights, including the necessity of informed consent. Among these are: *the Health Law, the Code of Ethics for Medical and Pharmaceutical Workers, the Law on Patients' Rights and Responsibilities*, etc.

- ✓ In Article 23 of the Health Law of the Republic of Moldova from March 28, 1995, it is stipulated that: “(1) Patient consent is required for any proposed medical service (preventive, diagnostic, therapeutic, rehabilitative); (2) In the absence of opposition, consent is assumed for any service that does not present significant risks to the patient or that is not likely to harm their privacy; (3) Consent for a patient under judicial protection is given by the person responsible for the protection; in their absence, by the closest relative; (4) Consent for a patient under judicial protection is presumed in cases of imminent danger of death or serious health threat; (5) Provisions of paragraphs (1), (2), (3), (4) apply to patients who have reached the age of 16; (6) If the patient is under 16 years old, consent is given by their legal representative. In cases of imminent danger of death or serious health threat, medical services may be carried out without the consent of the legal representative; (7) Patient consent or refusal, or that of their legal representative, is certified in writing, by the signature of the attending physician or the on-call team in exceptional cases, or by the signature of the management of the medical institution”.
- ✓ The Patients' Rights and Responsibilities Act of October 27, 2005, establishes a comprehensive framework outlining patients' rights, including their right to provide informed consent. Article 13 stipulates: „(1) A mandatory condition prior to any medical intervention is the patient's consent, except in cases provided by this law. (2) The patient's consent to medical intervention may be oral or written and is formalized by entering it into the patient's medical documentation, with mandatory signing by the patient or their legal representative (close relative) and the attending physician. For medical interventions with increased risk (invasive or surgical), consent must be in written form, by filling out a special form from the medical documentation, called informed consent. The list of

medical interventions requiring the completion of informed consent in written form and the model of the respective form are developed by the Ministry of Health, Labor, and Social Protection”.

- ✓ Section three of the Code of Ethics for Medical Workers and Pharmacists (dated March 24, 2017) describes the methods and conditions under which patient consent must be obtained within the medical act, emphasizing the importance of fully and correctly informing patients about the proposed treatment.

Therefore, these regulations, along with many others, are fundamental for patients, guaranteeing an ethical dialogue, supporting transparency, and patient rights.

2.2. Protecting confidentiality

In Moldova, public regulations regarding patient data confidentiality ensure the protection of personal information and the maintenance of professional secrecy. Next, we will present some fundamental aspects of current legislation and ethical standards:

- ✓ „The Health Law No. 411-XIII of March 28, 1995 establishes norms regarding the confidentiality of information related to the patient’s health status. According to this law, all health professionals are required to maintain the confidentiality of all information obtained in the exercise of their profession”.
- ✓ In the „Criminal Code of the Republic of Moldova,” adopted on April 18, 2002, includes „provisions that penalize the unlawful collection of personal data and the unauthorized disclosure of confidential information”.
- ✓ „Law No. 182 of July 10, 2008, which approves the Regulation of the National Center for Personal Data Protection”, outlines the legislative acts that establish the special protection regime for personal data.
- ✓ „Law No. 133 of July 8, 2011, on personal data protection”, „regulates the processing of personal data, including in the health sector, ensuring that processing is carried out in a manner that

respects the fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals, especially the right to privacy.”

- ✓ „The Code of Ethics for Physicians and Pharmacists” (2016) emphasizes the importance of maintaining professional secrecy and confidential information obtained within the doctor-patient relationship. Physicians are obligated not to disclose information about patients, except in cases provided by law.

Through these and other regulations, a balance is ensured between the need to protect both public health and the individual rights of patients, adhering to international ethical and legal standards. Referring to the support that public administration could provide in this context, we emphasize:

(1) He needs to develop new standards that would dictate the professional conduct of medical personnel; (2) funding and promoting education and training programs in bioethics for health professionals; (3) allocating funds for research in bioethics to analyze new ethical dilemmas and issues in medical communication; (4) facilitating dialogue between different public sectors for a comprehensive approach to bioethical issues.

In conclusion, through legislative and regulatory interventions, public institutions could ensure the protection of patient confidentiality and promote European standards in the healthcare sector.

Conclusions

In neurology, where the details of the interaction between the doctor and the patient are crucial, effective medical communication is vital for establishing an accurate diagnosis and implementing appropriate treatment. By obtaining informed consent, it is ensured that the patient is fully informed about treatment options, benefits, risks, and associated uncertainties, while respecting the bioethical principles of autonomy, non-maleficence, beneficence, and justice. Protecting confidentiality is another cornerstone of proper medical communication, essential for building and maintaining trust between patients and professionals. Revised public policies could regulate both informed consent and

confidentiality, ensuring the protection of patients' rights in medical or legal emergencies. As future recommendations, the need for close collaboration between healthcare professionals, patients, and public authorities stands out to adequately address new ethical and communication challenges.

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